

DESIGN AND FABRICATION OF MICRO EV BODY MADE OF GFRP

K. Sakata^{1*}, G. Ben¹ and H. Ohnishi²

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, College of Industrial Technology, NIHON University,
1-2-1 Izumi-cho, Narashino-shi, Chiba 275-8575, JAPAN,

² Graduate student of NIHON University

* Corresponding author(sakata.kazuhiro@nihon-u.ac.jp)

Keywords: *GFRP, Micro EV, Hand lay-up, Filament winding, VaRTM*

1 Introduction

Electric Vehicles (EVs) have been developing and fabricating in order to solve air pollution problems. EVs do not discharge CO₂ and NO_x during driving. Since the total number parts in EVs are less than those of gasoline cars, hybrid electric vehicles (HEVs) and fuel cell vehicles (FCVs), EVs are easily able to be developing by not only car companies but also small and medium- sized enterprises and some of universities [1-3]. However, their driving distance with one time full charge is relatively short. One method for solving this problem is a weight reduction of EVs body. We developed a micro EV made of GFRP by using manufacturing tools equipped with our laboratory and examined its driving performance.

2 Micro EVs

Micro EVs are small electric vehicles of a one-seater. Their dimensions are limited to 2.5 m in length, 1.3 m in width, and 2.0 m in height, respectively. The nominal power is from 0.25 kW to 0.6 kW and the maximum speed is under 60 km/h. Their running costs are less expensive than those of normal EVs.

3 Body shell

Since the body shape of our micro EV was decided a cylindrical one, a scraped water-retaining tank was used for a male mould in consideration of environmental recycling, low-cost and short-term fabrication hours. Its dimensions are 1.74 m in length, 1.12 m in width, and 0.48 m in height,

respectively. This mould was used to mold the upper and lower body shells.

To begin with, in order to make the finished surface smooth, the inner walls of the male mould were repaired. The NC surface was applied to them (Fig.1), and some hollow parts were repaired with patty. Then, all of the inner walls were polished with an air sander and waterproof sandpapers. Next, the inner walls of the male mould were applied with release agents, namely release wax and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA). After the PVA was cured, gelcoat was applied to the surface of release agents with a spray gun of the ratio of 600 g/m².

The body shells are molded by a method of a hand lay-up (Fig.2). The laminate sequence was surface mat / mat / woven roving / mat from the outsurface of body shell to the inside, and the total thickness was 2.7 mm. After the unsaturated polyester resin was cured, the laminated GFRP body shells were removed from the male mould with the compressed air and water. Fig.3 shows the upper body shell after the removal. Finally, the body shells were trimmed with the air sander and waterproof sandpapers. Their dimensions were 1.89 m in length, 1.12 m in width, and 0.880 m in height and their weights was 226 N.

3 Frame structure

3.1 Fabrication

A driver weight and in-cars parts were supported by a frame structure. The frame was composed of GFRP pipes and GFRP plates. Fig.4 shows the dimensions of the GFRP frame structure.

The GFRP pipes were molded by a 3-axis filament winding (FW) machine (Fig.5). Their winding angle was decided to 22° in consideration of the accuracy of fabrication in the FW machine. The thickness of

Fig.1 Application of NC surface

Fig.2 Hand lay-up process

Fig.3 Upper body shell before trimming

Fig.4 GFRP frame structure (unit:mm)

all the pipes was 2.8 mm and their thicknesses were decided based on the FEM analysis stated after.

First, a mandrel with 25 mm outside diameter was installed on the FW machine and release agent was applied five times to its surface. Next, Glass fiber roving impregnated with unsaturated polyester resin containing curing agent (1 wt%) was wound on the mandrel until the thickness of 2.8 mm. In order to reduce extra resin, its outermost layer after winding was wound peel ply materials. Finally, the GFRP pipe wound on the mandrel was cured one hour under 100 °C. After the resin was cured, the GFRP pipe was removed from the mandrel.

The plates were molded by a vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VaRTM) (Fig.6). The plates was fabricated with woven glass fiber / unsaturated polyester resin. Their dimensions were 700 mm in length, 600 mm in width, and 2.8 mm in thickness.

Fig.5 Filament winding

Fig.6 VaRTM process

Fig.8 GFRP overlay process

Fig.7 Edge of the pipe

Fig.9 Assembled frame

3.2 Joint

The GFRP pipes were jointed using a GFRP overlay. First, the pipes were cut to the prescribed length with a diamond cutter. The edge of the pipe was polished according to the outer shape of the connected pipe (Fig.7). Then, the GFRP pipes were bonded by a structural adhesive. In order to increase the joint strength, the joint parts were reinforced with the GFRP overlay (Fig.8). Fig.9 shows the assembled GFRP frame structure. Its dimensions were 1.2 m in length, 0.6 m in width, and 0.36 m in height, respectively and the weight was 181 N.

3.3 Comparison of FEM and experimental results

The FEM analysis was executed with ANSYS ver.11. Table 1 shows the material properties of GFRP. Due to symmetry in geometry and loading, one half of the frame was modeled. A driver weight (800N) and in-car parts (600N) were given to the point of 250 mm and 350 mm from the right and

left edges in the lower frame (Fig.10). The 4 node finite strain shell element (SHELL181) was used in the analysis. The total node numbers were 12201 and the total element numbers were 12330. A value of maximum deflection was 6.10 mm at 500 mm from the right of the lower frame.

In order to confirm a value of maximum deflection, a static load test of the assembled GFRP frame was executed. Four tire installation positions of the frame structure were simply supported and the loads of 600 N and 800 N were applied to the point of 250 mm and 350 mm from the right and left edges in the lower frame (Fig.11). A dial gauge was installed at 500 mm from the right edge in the lower frame and this point was supposed to be the maximum deflection point by the FEM analysis. The value of maximum deflection was 5.96 mm. This value was almost same value as the experimental value of 6.10 mm.

Table 1 Material properties of GFRP

GFRP pipe	Modulus of Elasticity	
	Longitudinal	45.1 GPa
	Transverse	12.7 GPa
	Sheer	4.71 GPa
	Poisson's Ratio	
	Longitudinal	0.25
	Transverse	0.07
GFRP plate	Modulus of Elasticity	
	Longitudinal	24.0 GPa
	Transverse	24.0 GPa
	Sheer	4.20 GPa
	Poisson's Ratio	
		Longitudinal
	Transverse	0.30

Fig.10 FEM analytical result

Fig.11 Static load test

4 Assembly

Fig.12 shows main electrical components and the wiring diagram. In-wheel motors were installed in the two rear wheels. Their motors were a brushless DC motor type. The maximum output and torque were 892.8 W and 64.3 Nm, respectively. Four batteries were connected in series and the rated voltage was 48 V. A full charge took 8 hours at 100 V.

Fig.13 shows the lower body and the frame structure without electrical components. The seat was made of GFRP. After electrical components were installed on the lower frame, the bolts and nuts were used to connect the upper and lower body shells. Fig.14 shows the assembled micro EV. The dimensions were 1.89 m in length, 1.29 m in width, and 0.95 m in height and the total weight was 1900 N.

Fig.12 Main electrical components

Fig.13 Lower body

Fig.14 Micro EV

Fig.15 Driving experiment

5 Driving experiments

In order to evaluate the driving performance of our micro EV, two types of driving experiments were executed.

The maximum speed was measured by the driving distance of 100 m. The driver's weight was 645 N. The micro EV accelerated from 0 to 50 m and the speed was calculated with the transit time from 50 to 100 m. The average maximum speed was 30.4 km/h. In order to measure the total driving distance with one time full charge, the experiment of long distance driving was executed in our university (Fig.15). A lap of the course in the experiment was 450 m. The average weight of three drivers was about 650 N. The total driving distance with one time full charge was 30 km. The continuous driving time was 2 hours and the average speed was 15.0 km/h. Table 2 lists the specifications of our micro EV.

6 Conclusions

1. The FRP body of our micro EV was fabricated in our laboratory without large scale of manufacturing equipments.
2. The development period from fabrication to driving experiments was about 6 months.
3. The average maximum speed was 30.4 km/h and the total driving distance with one time full charge was 30 km.

Table 2 Specifications

Dimensions	Length	1890 mm
	Width	1290 mm
	Height	950 mm
	Wheelbase	800 mm
	Tread front / rear	1180 mm / 1100 mm
	Ground clearance	100 mm
	Weight	1900 N
	Passengers	1
Performance	Maximum speed	30.4 km/h
	Charging time	8 h
	Driving distance	30 km
Motor	Type	Brushless DC In-wheel electric motor
	Rated voltage	48 V
	Maximum output	892.8 W
	Maximum torque	64.3 Nm
Battery	Type	Lead acid
	Total weight	688N
	Total voltage	48 V

References

- [1] H. Simizu "Electric Vehicle "Eliica" ". *Journal of the Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers*, Vol.108, No.1039, pp 450-451, 2005.
- [2] Y. Hashimoto "Development of small-sized electric vehicle with brake-by-wire". *Proceedings of the 45th annual meeting of JSME Chugoku-Shikoku Branch*, Japan, pp 389-390, 2008.
- [3] S. Matsumura "Lightweight Micro-EV in Low-Carbon Societies". *Proceedings of the 2009 Joint Conference of JSME Kanto Branch*, Japan, pp 171-172, 2009.